

Degradation Characteristics of Clays and Clay Minerals

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CLAY is basically the product of weathering or hydrothermal reaction of rocks. In general, clay means a natural fine grained earthy material which develops plasticity when mixed with limited amount of water¹. As a soil component, the term has a particle size connotation. Soil materials of particle size less than 2μ are broadly classed as clay. In fact, inorganic components of soil with particle size within this range include non-clay mineral substances as well. However, this fraction is the colloidal product of weathering and hence represents a very active portion of soil^{2,3,4}.

Conventional chemical analysis, study of ion exchange capacity, electrochemical and electrokinetic behaviour were successfully employed in the characterisation of clays^{1,5}. The crystalline structure of clay minerals was established by such advanced techniques as X-ray diffraction, differential thermal analysis, electron microscopy etc.¹.

A broad summary of the results of these studies are outlined below. The present store of knowledge on clay minerals has been built up by the outstanding contributions of Bragg⁶, Pauling⁷, Gruner⁸, Brindley and Robinson⁹, Hoffmann *et al.*¹⁰, Marshall¹¹, Hendricks and Jefferson¹², Maugin¹³, Jackson and West¹⁴, McMurchy¹⁵, Barshad¹⁶, Walker¹⁷, Grim *et al.*¹⁸ and others. It is on the basis of these works that the review is made.

The principal building elements of clay minerals are two dimensional arrays of silicon-oxygen tetrahedra and two-dimensional arrays of aluminium or magnesium-oxygen-hydroxyl octahedra. In most clay minerals such sheets of octahedra and of tetrahedra are superimposed in different fashions. In the silicon oxygen sheets, each silicon atom is coordinated with four oxygen atoms. The oxygen atoms are situated at the four corners of a regular tetrahedron with silicon atom at the centre. In the sheet, three of the four oxygen atoms of each tetrahedron were shared by three neighbouring tetrahedra. Therefore, the silicon tetrahedra are joined together in the a,b-directions to form a hexagonal net-work which is repeated indefinitely to form a sheet. The fourth oxygen atom of each tetrahedron is pointed perpendicular to the sheet.

In the octahedral sheet, the aluminium or magnesium atoms are co-ordinated with six oxygen

atoms or hydroxyl groups which are located around aluminium or magnesium atoms on the six corners of a regular octahedron. The sharing of the oxygen atoms by neighbouring octahedra results in a sheet. The oxygen atoms and the hydroxyl groups lie in two parallel planes with the aluminium or magnesium atoms between these planes. The projection of the sheet reveals that the oxygen atoms and the hydroxyl groups form a hexagonal close packing.

With aluminium in the octahedral position only two-thirds of the positions are filled up to balance the structure. It is the gibbsite structure and has the bulk formula $Al_2(OH)_6$. When magnesium is present in the octahedral co-ordination, all the possible positions are filled up giving the brucite structure having the bulk formula $Mg_3(OH)_6$.

Kaolinite :

This is formed by the superimposition of one layer of gibbsite sheet upon a layer of silica sheet in such a way that the octahedral oxygen atoms satisfy the fourth valency of silicon. The a,b-dimensions of silicon tetrahedron and aluminium octahedron are of the same order of magnitude so that a layer is easily formed. This composite sheet is the unit sheet of kaolinite minerals. These sheets which are continuous in the a,b-directions are stacked, one above the other, in the c-direction. The successive sheets are probably held together by a somewhat, stronger and more specific linkage than would be provided solely by van der Waals forces.

The variation between the members of kaolin group is in the way of stacking of the unit layers and possibly in the positions of the aluminium atom in the successive position open to them in the octahedral layer.

Montmorillonite :

The montmorillonites are essentially composed of three sheets. Two layers of silicon tetrahedra are superimposed over a central sheet of aluminium octahedra. The tips of all the silicon tetrahedra and one layer of the hydroxyl group from the aluminium form a common layer. The atoms common to tetrahedral and octahedral layers become oxygen instead of hydroxyl groups.

The minerals of this group are developed by stacking of these units, one above the other in the c-direction. During stacking the oxygen layers of one unit are close to the oxygen layers of other unit so that there is an excellent cleavage between the sheets. Polar molecules can enter the space between the sheets and thus cause the expansion of the axis in the c-direction. Isomorphous substitution of aluminium takes place in the octahedral sheet by Mg^{+2} or such ions as Fe^{+2} , Cr^{+3} , Zn^{+2} , Li^+ etc. giving rise to a net negative charge on the clay lattice. In the tetrahedral layer also silicon is partly replaced by aluminium.

Illite :

Illite is also a three-layer clay. The basic structural units of illite mineral are the same as that of the montmorillonites. These are, however, distinguished from the montmorillonites primarily by the absence of interlayer swelling in presence of water or polar organic liquids.

Isomorphous replacement in illite occurs mainly in the tetrahedral layer, some of silicon being always replaced by aluminium. The non-swelling characteristic of illite clays is attributed to a specific bonding of unit layers by potassium ions. These ions are of the right size to establish a favourable 12 co-ordination with opposite hexagonal oxygen rings of adjacent unit layers, being embedded snugly into the spaces created by the opposite holes. The unit layers do not part away on addition of water. The potassium ions between the unit layers are thus not available for exchange and they are fixed. The potassium ions in the external surfaces only can be exchanged.

Decomposition or degradation of clays and clay minerals :

Hydrogen clays as reported first by Paver and Marshall¹⁹ and later by others (Chatterjee & Paul²⁰; Mukherjee *et al.*²¹; Harward & Coleman²²; Low²³; Mitra & Singh²⁴; Eeckman & Laudelot²⁵; Coleman & Craig²⁶) are spontaneously converted into hydrogen aluminium clays, the temperature (Coleman & Craig²⁶; Chernov *et al.*²⁷; Laudelot & Eeckman²⁸; Davies *et al.*²⁹) and chemical composition of the clay (Alldrich & Buchanan³⁰; Chernov³¹; Barshaad³²) being the factors which influence the rate of transformation. This spontaneous transformation, according to Eeckman & Laudelot²⁵, indicates an interdiffusion of hydrogen and aluminium ions. The aluminium ions diffuse from the edges of crystals towards the centre against an equivalent flow of hydrogen ions, adsorbed on the faces of crystals, which react immediately with the lattice as soon as they have reached the edge of the clay particle, although Slabaugh³³ reports that the hydrogen ions from the absorbed ion layer of hydrogen clay migrate into the lattice and are bound to positions which

are closer to cation exchange site. According to Mitra & Singh²⁴ the aluminium ions in the octahedral position are mobilised laterally by the exchangeable hydrogen ions and exchange positions for the latter.

The spontaneous transformation of hydrogen clays into hydrogen aluminium clays is no doubt a characteristic feature but the decomposition or degradation of clay minerals in acids, alkalis and other chemical agents or by other means is fundamentally important because it reveals certain attributes of the clay mineral and certain differences between them which are not obvious from other methods of study. The decomposition or degradation characteristics of clay minerals are very important in determining the limitations of such treatment like acids etc. in elucidating the mechanism of such reactions and in determining their ion exchange property. Numerous workers studied on these aspects and their observations are discussed systematically.

Decomposition or degradation of clays and clay minerals in acid :

The decomposition or degradation of the clay minerals in acids varies with the nature of the acid, the acid concentration, the acid to clay ratio, the temperature, and the duration of treatment. Also the decomposition or degradation of various clay mineral groups is quite different and there is great variation in decomposition or degradation characteristics of members of some individual groups.

According to Nutting³⁴, who has made a detailed study of the solubility of clay minerals, several stages of decomposition can be distinguished, although they merge into one another under many sets of conditions. At equilibrium, a fraction of the acid or alkali remains free and a fraction of each clay remains undissolved regardless of the proportions present. Over a range of low acid concentrations 0.05 to 0.2 normal, the solution is essentially a silicate hydrosol similar in composition to the clay dissolved. At higher concentration it contains also salts in solution; at lower concentrations excess silica. At acid concentrations of 20% and over, bases but no silica go into solution and no hydrosols are formed.

Pask and Davies³⁵ found that 20% sulphuric acid at boiling temperature for 1 hour dissolved only 3% of the alumina from kaolinite, 9% from anaxite, 11% from illite, 17% from muscovite, 33 to 87% from montmorillonite and 50 to 90% of halloysite. They also observed the variations in the solubility of these clay minerals in sulphuric acid of the same concentration under different temperatures. Thiebaut³⁶ compared the solubility of biotite, kaolinite, montmorillonite, muscovite and halloysite in hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid under almost similar conditions.

According to Thiebaut, the solubility of these minerals was complete in sulphuric acid, but partial in hydrochloric acid, the solubility being based on their cation solubility.

Investigations of anion exchange indicate that the solubility is likely to be considerable, especially for the acids with an anion having a size and geometry approximating that of the component parts of the clay mineral lattice. As a consequence, some relatively weak acids may strongly attack certain clay minerals. Murray³⁷ showed, for example, that phosphoric acid attacks the kaolinite lattice under some conditions with greater vigour than sulphuric acid. Also fluoride solutions attack kaolinite much more strongly than might otherwise be expected, the first stage in the process being an exchange of surface hydroxyl groups for fluoride as demonstrated by Dickman & Bray³⁸. Wolf³⁹ reported that the solubility of clay minerals in acid depends on acid concentration.

Carroll and Starkey⁴⁰ percolated water saturated with carbon dioxide at 25°C, through layers of limestone alternating with montmorillonite, illite and kaolinite for long periods of time. They found silica only in the leachate, and the minerals lost silica in the order montmorillonite > kaolinite > illite.

Ostrom⁴¹ studied the solubility of clay minerals in various acids, mainly hydrochloric and acetic acid at different concentrations. He found that treatment of either hectorite, chlorite or mixed layer illite-montmorillonite with either hydrochloric or acetic acid of moderate concentration causes a slight change in X-ray diffraction data. Kaolinite and illite are unaffected even though at relatively higher acid concentration.

Brindley⁴² pointed out that fine grained chlorites decompose in warm dilute hydrochloric acid whereas kaolinite is not ordinarily decomposed by this treatment. He pointed out further that chemical composition of chlorite and particle size, as well as acid concentration, time and temperature are important in acid solubility. Oberlin *et al.*⁴³ found that kaolinite subjected to a prolonged treatment with sulphuric acid solutions at pH 2 resulted in the appearance of poorly crystallized kaolinite. Their study showed a tendency for the bonds between the silicate layers to be ruptured, followed by gliding along b-axis, thus indicating the presence of a considerable number of protons between silicate sheets which are responsible for a large amount of the bonding.

Escard *et al.*⁴⁴ discussed the X-ray diffraction characteristics of montmorillonite that develop with increasing attack by acids. Haden⁴⁵ showed that pugging kaolinite with concentrated sulphuric acid and then roasting at about 300°C result in the

formation of aluminium sulphate from which the aluminium may be readily leached with water.

Carroll & Starkey⁴⁶ studied hydrochloric and acetic acid attack on some clay minerals like monmorillonite, halloysite etc. X-ray examinations showed that the acid treatment did not destroy clay structure, except for halloysite which underwent partial decomposition. In the attack on smectite clay minerals and probably also on the illite and sepiolite attapulgite clay minerals, it appears that the alkalis and alkaline earths are removed relatively more rapidly than the aluminium or iron and the iron is removed more rapidly than the aluminium. Mathers *et al.*⁴⁷ reported that aluminium, iron and magnesium were removed from smectites they studied in the same proportions as they occurred in the mineral. On the other hand, Nikolaev *et al.*⁴⁸ found that repeated treatments of vermiculite with normal nitric acid reduced the magnesium and iron at a much higher rate than that of aluminium. According to them, the removal of magnesium and iron had only a small effect on the cation exchange capacity whereas in the case of aluminium, the cation exchange capacity was reduced in proportion to the reduction in the aluminium content.

The mechanism of vigorous attack by acids has been studied by X-ray methods. Thus Hofmann & Endell⁴⁹, Glaeser⁵⁰ and Mering⁵¹ showed that 75-85% of the total alumina must be lost from the montmorillonite lattice before it is completely destroyed. The tetrahedral part of the structure as well as the octahedral part tends to disintegrate on acid attack which begins around the edges of the particles and works inwards.

Support for this concept is afforded by the rate of solution in hydrochloric acid experiments of Brindley & Youell⁵² on chlorites and by those of Osthau⁵³ on nontronite and montmorillonite. Such studies make it possible to determine by chemical means the metallic ions present in tetrahedral and in octahedral co-ordination and also reveal that the aluminium in octahedral co-ordination is more attacked in hydrochloric acid than the aluminium in tetrahedral co-ordination.

Gastuche & Fripiat⁵⁴ observed that, after the octahedral layer of the clay minerals has been removed, the (001) reflections persist indicating retention of order in the tetrahedral layer.

It appears that the removal of aluminium is stepwise, i.e., it moves first from octahedral positions to exchange positions and then to complete solubility. If the sample is dried before all the aluminium is removed, at least, some of it appears to move back from exchange positions to octahedral positions. Mathers *et al.*⁴⁷ found that the hydrogen montmorillonites changed spontaneously into aluminium clays. The rate of conversion was slow at

0° but at temperatures at about 100°, moist hydrogen montmorillonite changed to aluminium saturated montmorillonite within 24 hours. It appeared that octahedral aluminium moved more rapidly from the lattice to exchange positions than tetrahedral aluminium.

Cloos *et al.*⁵⁵ were also able to differentiate between octahedral and tetrahedral components on the basis of acid solubility. Gastuche & Fripiat⁵⁴ found that the differential attack on octahedral layers as compared with tetrahedral layers was improved by using solutions of acid saturated with silica.

Osthaus⁵⁶ concluded from the study of acid attack on the lattice of montmorillonite that the reaction was of first order. Studies by Langston & Jenne⁵⁶ and Miller⁵⁷ indicated that the order rate law is not necessarily the same for all clay minerals or even for members of the same species. Wide variations in rate constants were found for specimens of the same clay mineral, depending on particle size, crystallinity etc. Kerr *et al.*⁵⁸ studied the degradation of hectorite by hydrogen ions and concluded that two consecutive first order reactions occurred :

(i) Strong acid underwent a rapid spontaneous reaction to yield weak acid and (ii) the resulting weak acid underwent a slow spontaneous reaction to yield a neutral clay. A tentative mechanism was also suggested.

Neumann⁵⁹ studied the degradation of montmorillonite caused by the extraction of structural cations by acids, using thermogravimetric analysis. She considered two hypotheses : one based on the coexistence of residual montmorillonite and silica gel as separate entities and another on the assumption that the acid attack takes place uniformly throughout the structure, leading to montmorillonite with various concentrations of vacant octahedral positions. She concluded that the evidence strongly favoured the second hypothesis.

Murray³⁷ showed that under similar conditions of treatment the actual sulphate or phosphate compound resulting from treatment with sulphuric or phosphoric acid respectively, is almost the same for all kaolinites and halloysite, regardless of variations in degree of crystallinity. There were, however, some differences which suggested to him that the structural attributes of the parent clay minerals exert some influence on the nature of the resulting reaction product.

The structural decomposition of an orthochlorite mineral by acid and kinetics of its acid dissolution was reported by Ross^{60,61}. Numan Abdul-Latif & Weaver⁶² digested palygorskite and sepiolite with large excess of hydrochloric acid at constant temperature for various periods of time. The reaction

was found to be of first order with respect to magnesium, aluminium and iron components in the clay and also with respect to hydrochloric acid concentration. According to Ross⁶⁰, the acid dissolution of chlorite in 2N silicon saturated hydrochloric acid showed that there was no preferential dissolution of aluminium in octahedral positions and that the octahedral and tetrahedral sheets in the chlorite structure were equally attacked. Microscopic examination showed, however, that the acid attack was not simply an edge attack, but started at any point where cracks, structural defects and weaknesses apparently predisposed sites to acid attack.

Gilkes *et al.*⁶⁴ reported the weathering of oxidised biotite in hydrochloric acid and its rate of dissolution in hydrochloric acid at different concentrations. Gilkes & Young⁶⁵ also pointed out that the presence of 1M K⁺ in solution reduced dissolution rates of oxidised biotites in 0.1; 0.01M HCl to approximately 10% and 20% respectively of the rates in dilute acid alone. Large difference in dissolution rate of biotite due to oxidation of structural iron persisted in the presence of K⁺.

Barnhisal & Rostromel⁶⁶ observed that when kaolinite and illite were shaken for upto six months with 0.01-5N H₂SO₄, the acid attacked both clays at the edges. Al, Fe, K, Si and possibly other ions were released to the solution phase. With illite the octahedral layer appeared to dissolve faster than the tetrahedral layer and the dissolution of octahedral layer cations preceded K release. The dissolution rates of both minerals are similar.

Boyle *et al.*⁶⁷ studied the weathering of biotite by organic acids such as oxalic, malonic, citric, malic, propionic and lactic. The amounts of K, Fe, Mg and Al extracted increased with time. The ratios of Fe, Mg or Al to K in the solution were greater than one but decreased with increasing extraction time. The organic acids extracted greater percentages of cations than hydrochloric acid did.

Experimental investigations of chemical weathering in which powders of K-feldspar, albite, brucite, muscovite, tremolite, olivine and volcanic glass are treated with pure water and dilute solutions of sulphuric, carbonic and hydrochloric acid have been performed by Correns⁶⁸ in an apparatus in which the mineral powder is exposed to a circulating water flow. The experiments have been continued recently by treating kaolinite and montmorillonite. The course of decomposition of these minerals depends on water flow rate, grain size, temperature and pH of solutions. These experiments in open systems are compared with investigations reported in the literature and with the conditions of natural weathering.

Schnitzer & Kodama⁶⁹ reported the dissolution of micas by fulvic acid (FA). Three micas commonly

occurring in soils, that is, biotite, phlogopite and muscovite were shaken with 0.2% (w/v) aq. FA solution for 710 hours at room temperature. Major constituent elements extracted were Fe, Al, Mg, K and Si from biotite, Al, Mg, K and Si from phlogopite and Al, K and Si from muscovite. The ease with which the micas were attacked by FA decreased in the following order :

biotite > phlogopite > muscovite

Decomposition or degradation of clays and clay minerals in alkali :

There has been very little study of the solubility of the clay minerals in alkalis. Nutting³⁴ studied particularly the solubility of montmorillonite and attapulgite in dilute solutions of sodium carbonate. His results for montmorillonite show that for this clay mineral, the amount of silica removed in solution increases as the concentration of sodium carbonate increases to a maximum at about 0.025% sodium carbonate concentration. At higher concentrations, the solubility decreases to a minimum at about 0.05% sodium carbonate and then rises steadily to 0.70 g/lit at 1% sodium carbonate concentration. According to Nutting, only silica is dissolved by the alkali up to a concentration of 0.05% sodium carbonate. He pointed out that an extremely dilute solution of alkali is very effective in removing silica from montmorillonites and, given enough time, probably could remove all of it. The relative amount of silica dissolved is lower for the attapulgite than montmorillonite.

Foster⁷⁰ studied the solubility of montmorillonite in sodium hydroxide of various concentrations and presented a method for determining free silica and alumina, based on solubility in 0.05N solutions. Carroll and Starkey⁴⁶ treated some clay minerals such as montmorillonite, illite, kaolinite, halloysite etc. with sodium hydroxide for some period. According to them, kaolinite and halloysite were only attacked, as shown by chemical analysis, x-ray etc.

The influence of an alkaline environment on clay mineral alterations in the laboratory was studied by Ferrell Jr. & Grim, using one-dimensional structural analysis. Samples of illite, illite-mixed-layered material, kaolinite and two montmorillonites were treated with NH₄OH solutions of pH 8.5, 9.5, 10.5, 11.5 & 12.5 for 6, 12, 24, 48, 72 & 96 hours at 60°C. One-dimensional structural analyses of the treated samples are quite demonstrative in determining the effects of laboratory controlled degradation. These analyses show an oscillatory change in the population of tetrahedral and octahedral structural sites which is consistent with a core rind structural concept of clay minerals. Leaching of clay minerals takes place by alternate growth of the rind and destruction of this frayed edge by agitation. The extent to which the rind develops is controlled by particle size, variability of chemical composition

and the amount of agitation. The sequence of increasing development of the frayed edge is : kaolinite, illite, illite-mixed-layered material and then the montmorillonite.

Decomposition or degradation of clays and clay minerals by other chemical agents or by other means :

Numerous investigators have indicated that electro dialysis of some of the clay minerals may cause their decomposition. Thus Kelley⁷² showed that as the cations are replaced by hydrogen ions, aluminium ions move from octahedral positions to exchange positions. Hofmann & Geise⁷³ showed that, in general, non-exchangeable cations are lost from within the lattice before all the exchangeable cations are replaced by hydrogen ion.

The amount of loss of non-exchangeable cations during electro dialysis varies with the clay mineral. Magnesium-rich smectite minerals seem to be most susceptible, and Nutting⁷⁴ showed that all the magnesium can be removed from hectorite by electro dialysis with complete breakdown of the structure. Caldwell & Marshall⁷⁵ showed that the same results are obtained with saponite. Other smectites are quite susceptible to such alteration. The iron-rich smectites are more susceptible than those high in aluminium.

Attapulgite-sepiolite, vermiculite, chlorite and some of the biotite micas are quite susceptible to disintegration by electro dialysis. Roy⁷⁶ showed that prolonged electro dialysis decomposed biotite with extensive loss of octahedral cations as well as of potassium. Kaolinite is relatively little affected by electro dialysis.

Repeated desaturations and treatments with salts like barium chloride were studied by Mukherjee *et al.*^{77,78}, using a number of clays from Indian soils as well as montmorillonite, kaolinite and pyrophyllite. Repeated cycles of treatment caused a decrease in the aluminium liberated and a smaller decrease in the hydrogen, so that finally the ratio of hydrogen released to aluminium released became large. Successive treatments eventually caused a large reduction in the cation exchange capacity of montmorillonite, indicating considerable decomposition which was confirmed by the appearance of soluble silica in the earlier desaturations. With kaolinite, aluminium and hydrogen were similarly brought into solution, but their release caused no measurable reduction in exchange capacity. The work of Mukherjee *et al.* shows the extreme sensitivity of some of the clay minerals to salt treatment.

It is well-known that hydrogen clays prepared in the usual way 'age' during preparation but more thoroughly with time. During the process of ageing, it may be assumed that aluminium ions exchange for hydrogen ions in the clays, so that ultimately the latter contains appreciable amounts of mobilised

aluminium ions. On passing the hydrogen aluminium clays through a column of hydrogen resin, aluminium ions will be replaced by hydrogen ions. The resulting hydrogen clay on ageing would again mobilise the aluminium ions. One would imagine that if this process of ageing and passing through hydrogen resin column is repeated, the resulting hydrogen clay would reach a stage when, as a result of the removal of appreciable amount of mobilisable aluminium ions, it would show signs of degradation. Compared with other methods of removing exchangeable aluminium ions, the hydrogen resin which removes exchangeable aluminium ions would not probably attack clay lattice otherwise. The study of the characteristics of the hydrogen clays formed at every stage will throw considerable light on the mechanism of the reactions involving removal of aluminium ions. In fact, a degradation of the kind envisaged has been confirmed by Majumdar & Mukherjee⁷⁹, using three hydrogen montmorillonites differing in their chemical compositions owing to isomorphous substitution. The three hydrogen montmorillonites show visible signs of degradation of their lattices at the edges and planar surfaces as indicated from X-ray diffraction, differential thermal, chemical and electrometric analyses and determination of free oxide. The following changes in their nature, behaviour and characteristics are observed: marked colour change, appreciable pH lowering, loss of dispersive character and formation of flocs, often of a thixotropic gel. The free oxide contents of the montmorillonites are increased as well as their water holding capacities. Considerable amounts of aluminium, iron, magnesium and other octahedral cations are removed from the lattices followed by redistribution of electrical charges in the tetrahedral and octahedral layers. They also exhibit a gradual change from weak acid to strong acid character (Figure 1⁷⁹). The titratable acidities due to hydrogen ions increase while those due to aluminium and other ions, and cation exchange capacities decrease. Silicic acid gel or sol, alumina gel, ferric oxide gel, oxyhydroxides of iron and aluminium or hydroxides of aluminium are probably formed. The three hydrogen montmorillonites differ widely in the nature and extent of the degradation of their lattices because of differences in their lattice substitution and initial structural peculiarities. Majumdar⁸⁰ reported that hydrogen kaolinite on successive cycles of aging and passing through hydrogen resin column⁷⁹ shows degradation of its lattice at the edges.

The effect of sea water on clay minerals was studied by Carroll and Starkey⁸¹. Samples of a montmorillonite, a mixed layer mineral (mica and montmorillonite), illite, kaolinite and halloysite were immersed in 50 ml sea water for 10 days and additional samples of first three were immersed for 150 days. The exchangeable cations were determined both before and after treatment. It was found that Mg^{+2} ions from sea water moved into the exchange positions in the minerals in preference to Ca^{+2} and

Fig. 1. pH titration curves f, g, h, i, j and k of hydrogen bentonite from Bihar after 0, 20, 30, 50, 70 and 90 cycles of aging and passing through hydrogen resin column respectively according to Majumdar and Mukherjee⁷⁹.

Na^{+} ions. The H-form of these minerals showed a gradual adjustment to sea water as measured by change in pH and filling of the exchange positions with cations other than H^{+} . Kaolinite adjusted very rapidly but montmorillonite and the mixed layer mineral slowly. All the minerals reacted to yield appreciable amounts of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 to the sea water. The quantities yielded are in the order:

The solubility is considered to be due to direct solution of SiO_2 in the sea water and to removal of Al_2O_3 from the octahedral layer of minerals.

Mokma *et al.*⁸² studied the weathering of muscovite macroflakes by salt treatment. Election micrographs showed that the muscovite surface had been etched and a sesquioxide weathering product is formed. The artificial weathering of oxidised biotite by sodium tetraphenylboron has been reported by Gilkes *et al.*⁸³. X-ray diffraction patterns

of potassium depleted biotites show that more extensive formation of hydrobiotite occurs as the proportion of structural ferric iron in biotite increases. The weathering of clay minerals like illite etc. by sodium tetraphenylboron was also reported by Adhikari & Majumdar⁸⁴.

Information about the weathering of vermiculite and biotite flakes by chemical and biological agents was given by Sawhney & Voigt⁸⁵ and Boyl *et al.*⁸⁶. In case of vermiculite, there was the production of a bleached weathered edge amorphous to X-ray. Conyers *et al.*⁸⁷ studied the influence of chemical weathering on basal spacings of some clay minerals like illite, vermiculite etc.

The weathering of hornblende, augite, phlogopite, muscovite, albite and andesine as influenced by Ca, Mg, K, Na, NH₄, Al & H was studied by Andersson & Wiklander⁸⁸ for two years. Extractable amounts of Al and Fe decreased during the second year. The reason is supposed to be precipitation of hydroxides followed by a gradual recrystallisation to more resistant compounds. Hence it is not possible to estimate the total mobilisation of these ions. Based on the release, the following stability sequence could be arranged :

hornblende < augite < albite < muscovite < phlogopite < andesine.

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